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Gold wealth and extraction methods: the contribution of local populations to the gold industry in Burkina Faso

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ABSTRACT

Burkina Faso, a West African country, is located between two climatic zones, the Sahelian zone and the Sudanese zone. The southern part of the country (Sudano-Guinean zone) receives the most rainfall (1,100 mm) annually, the center (Sudano-Sahelian zone) receives 800 mm/year, and the Sahel region receives 500 mm of water per year. Gold mining in Burkina Faso is characterized by industrial, artisanal, and semi-mechanized exploitation. Mining and artisanal sites are spread throughout the country. Industrial mining is mainly dominated by foreign companies, while artisanal mining is carried out by nationals. In this article, we highlight the country's gold potential, as well as the means, methods, and techniques used in mining and the living conditions of gold miners. However, recurring conflicts between industrial and artisanal mining operations and the insecurity affecting the country are having a significant impact on Burkina Faso's mining sector.

Keywords: Burkina Faso, Gold potential, Gold mining, Gold manner, Mine

INTRODUCTION

The land of honest men, formerly known as Upper Volta, is a former French colony created in 1919 and renamed Burkina Faso by revolutionary captain Thomas Isidore Noël Sankara in 1984. During slavery, the slaves of Upper Volta provided the physical labor required for agricultural work, mining, livestock farming, and security services. Senegalese riflemen composed of Voltaics fought alongside France during the First World War in 1919 and the Second World War in 1939.

In 1958, Upper Volta joined the French Community and two years later gained independence on August 5, 1960, with Maurice YAMEOGO as President. Since independence, several political regimes alternating between constitutional republics and military regimes (seven coups d'état) have succeeded one another in the country. First Republic Maurice YAMEOGO (1960-1966); military regime Sanguilé LAMIZANA (1966-1970); Second Republic: a new constitution and return to civilian rule (1970-1974); military coup (military putsch overthrows the regime) (1974-1977). The Third Republic (1977-1980): a new constitution; a military coup takes power (1980-1983) following strikes.

In August 1983, revolution and the Fourth Republic of Thomas Isidore Noël SANKARA (1983-1987); the Blaise COMPAORE era (1987-2014); post-Blaise COMPAORE transition Michel KAFANDO (2014-2015); the presidency of Roch Marc Christian KABORE (2016-2022).

In January 2022, a transition led by Paul-Henri Sandaogo DAMIBA took place, and on September 30 of the same year, he was overthrown by his brothers in arms, with Captain Ibrahim TRAORE at the head of the country to this day. Faced with the phenomenon of terrorism since 2015, which caused the fall of Kabore and Damiba's power, attacks are becoming less and less frequent throughout the country (**Map 1**) [1-11].

Burkina Faso has enormous gold potential due to its gently undulating geological base adorned with lateritic armored hills, and much of the country is located on a Precambrian Birrian rift (**Map 2**) [12].

Map 1. Location of Burkina Faso in Africa and the world.

Map 2. Geological structure of Burkina Faso.

The Burkinabe rift is composed of metamorphic rocks (mainly schistose) and iron-rich lateritic crusts. Volcanic sedimentary formations are also present, giving the country abundant mineral resources (**Photos 1 to 5**) [12].

The policies and laws adopted in particular in 1984 during the revolution, in the 1990s, and in 2015 during the transition have attracted foreign private companies to invest in Burkina Faso's mining sector [8-10]. A variety of actors are involved in gold mining. The gold sector in Burkina Faso has two modes of exploitation: industrial and artisanal (**Photos 6-9**) [13-20].

Constraints in the sector have led to a third mode of exploitation, semi-mechanized mining, resulting in three modes of gold mining in the country of honest men (**Photos 10-12**). All of these methods encompass several types of mining, namely open-pit mining and underground mining for industrial mines (**Photos 13-23**).

This type of mining relies on specific and appropriate resources, equipment, techniques, and methods. As for artisanal mining, also known as gold panning, it is organized around a site generally located on or upstream of a hill where galleries (holes) can be found in which gold panners (miners) extract the ore.

This corresponds to vein mining, in river beds (alluvial mining), in gravel areas (dredging) and using detectors for artisanal mining or gold panning (**Photos 24-55**) [21-27].

The ore is transported to a site called yaar (Moore local language) for processing. The means of transport vary depending on whether it is industrial or artisanal mining (**Photos 56-62**). The yaar is the place where the rocks are kept in bags and stored in a safe place for the owner (**Photos 63-69**). The rock is crushed using archaic or traditional methods, but also using modern methods (**Photos 70-74**). Grinding is carried out by a group of people using mills installed in the yaar (**Photos 75-81**). Halfway through the sinking process, the gold miners test the gold content of the ore using an iron mortar and pestle (**Photos 82-84**).

The washing of the ore is done by both men and women and requires appropriate equipment (**Photos 85-92**) [28-33]. Cyniir is another form of re-exploitation of ore residues that have already been mined at least once (**Photos 93-97**). Gold is also sold at the processing site, and its weight is measured using digital measuring devices and local scales (**Photos 98-100**). Electrical equipment and drilling installations are also present to meet the gold mining site's electricity and water needs (**Photos 101-106**). The yaar (site) is home to the gold miners' houses, shops, restaurants, butchers, maquis, places of worship, and toilets (**Photos 107-124**). The gold miners are men and women, adults and children, mainly from Burkina Faso, with no distinction between ethnic groups [34-39].

CONCLUSION

Gold mining is carried out throughout Burkina Faso, in all regions of the country except for the central region, which is the capital. The gold boom has made gold the country's leading export product. There are 15 industrial mines in operation, with 15 mining permits granted. As for gold panning, there are currently around 800 artisanal mining sites, most of which are informal, and around 30 sites with formal mining permits across the country. According to ANEMAS, there will be an estimated 2 million artisanal miners in 2024. However, artisanal mining faces many difficulties linked to terrorism, which the national authorities consider to be a source of funding for terrorists. The lack of control over gold panning has therefore led to the suspension of this form of mining during the rainy seasons.

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Appendix

Photo 1. Hill where gold panning takes place in Réo,
(Photograph by Nama Mathieu, 2025).

Photo 2. Gold panning hill in Réo,
(Photographed by Nama Mathieu, 2025).

Photo 3. Gold panning site in Réo,
(Photographed by Nama Mathieu, 2025).

Photo 4. Industrial gold mining hill.
Source: BUMIGEB.

Photo 5. Industrial gold mining hill.
Source: BUMIGEB.

Photo 6. Artisanal gold mining in Houndé,
(Photographed by Nama Mathieu, 2025).

Photo 7. Artisanal gold mining in Houndé,
(Photographed by Nama Mathieu, 2025).

Photo 8. Industrial gold mining in Youga,
Source: BUMIGEB

Photo 9. Industrial gold mining in Yaramako,
Source: BUMIGEB

Photo 10. Semi-mechanised gold mining in Réo,
(Photographed by Nama Mathieu, 2025).

Photo 11. Semi-mechanised gold mining in Réo,
(Photographed by Nama Mathieu, 2025).

Photo 12. Semi-mechanised gold mining,
Source: FAMAB.

Photo 13. Open-pit gold mining,
Source: MEMC.

Photo 14. Open-pit gold mining,
Source: MEMC.

Photo 15. Open-pit gold mining,
Source: MEMC.

Photo 16. Open-pit gold mining,
Source: MEMC.

Photo 17. Open-pit gold mining,
Source: MEMC.

Photo 18. Open-pit gold mining,
Source: MEMC.

Photo 19. Open-pit gold mining,
Source: MEMC.

Photo 20. Underground industrial mining,
Source: MEMC.

Photo 21. Underground gold mining,
Source: MEMC.

Photo 22. Underground industrial mining,
Source: Google

Photo 23. Underground industrial mining,
Source: Google

Photo 24. Artisanal open-pit mining in Réo,
(Photographed by Nama Mathieu, 2025).

Photo 25. Artisanal open-pit mining in Réo,
(Photographed by Nama Mathieu, 2025).

Photo 26. Artisanal open-pit mining in Réo,
(Photographed by Nama Mathieu, 2025).

Photo 27. Artisanal open-pit mining in Réo,
(Photographed by Nama Mathieu, 2025).

Photo 28. Artisanal open-pit mining in Réo,
(Photographed by Nama Mathieu, 2025).

Photo 29. Artisanal open-pit mining in Réo,
(Photographed by Nama Mathieu, 2025).

Photo 30. Artisanal open-pit mining in Réo,
(Photographed by Nama Mathieu, 2025).

Photo 31. Artisanal open-pit mining in Réo,
(Photographed by Nama Mathieu, 2025).

Photo 32. Artisanal open-pit mining in Réo,
(Photographed by Nama Mathieu, 2025).

Photo 33. Artisanal open-pit mining,
by Dera Abasse, 2023.

Photo 34. Artisanal open-pit mining,
by Dera Abasse, 2023.

Photo 35. Open-air artisanal mining
by Dera Abasse, 2024.

Photo 36. Open-air artisanal mining
by Dera Abasse, 2024.

Photo 37. Alluvial mining,
by Dera Abasse, 2024.

Photo 38. Alluvial mining,
by Dera Abasse, 2024.

Photo 39. Alluvial mining,
by Dera Abasse, 2024.

Photo 40. Vantage mining,
by Dera Abasse, 2024.

Photo 41. Vantage mining,
by Dera Abasse, 2024.

Photo 42. Vantage mining,
by Dera Abasse, 2024.

Photo 43. Operation by detection device,
by Dera Abasse, 2023.

Photo 44. Operation by device Detector,
Google, 2025.

Photo 45. Gold detector device,
Google, 2025.

Photo 46. Gold detector device,
Google, 2025.

Photos 47(A,B). Filionian extraction well with wood as a means of protection against rockfalls in Kari (Houndé), (Photographed by Nama Mathieu, 2022).

Photo 48. Filionian exploitation well in Dossi, by Dera Abasse, 2022.

Photo 49. Filionian exploitation well in Dossi,
by Dera Abasse, 2022.

Photo 50. Alignment of vein mining shafts in Kari (Houndé),
(Photographed by Nama Mathieu, 2022).

Photo 51. Alignment of vein mining shafts in Kari (Houndé),
(Photographed by Nama Mathieu, 2022).

Photo 52. Gold mining in Kamti (Gaoua),
by Dera Abasse, 2022.

Photo 53. Gold mining in Dossi (Houndé),
by Dera Abasse, 2022.

Photo 54. Underground vein mining with an air ventilation system powered by solar panels and batteries, (Photographed by Nama Mathieu, 2025).

Photo 55. Gold mining in Bouéré (Houndé)
by Dera Abasse, 2022.

Photo 56. Transport lorry,
Google 2025.

Photo 57. Transport lorry,
Google 2025.

Photo 58. Two-wheeled motorcycles as a means of transport,
(Photographed by Nama Mathieu, 2025).

Photo 59. A cart as a means of transporting ore,
(Photographed by Nama Mathieu, 2025).

Photo 60. A cart for transporting water to the treatment site,
(Photographed by Nama Mathieu, 2025).

Photo 61. A tricycle for all transport on Guido's gold site,
(Photographed by Nama Mathieu, 2025).

Photo 62. A tricycle for transporting equipment,
(Photographed by Nama Mathieu, 2025).

Photo 63. Ore stored in sacks,
(Photographed by Nama Mathieu, 2025).

Photo 64. Ore stored in piles and bags,
(Photographed by Nama Mathieu, 2025).

Photo 65. A pile stored during processing,
(Photographed by Nama Mathieu, 2025).

Photo 66. Ore residues preserved for future mining,
(Photographed by Nama Mathieu, 2025).

Photo 67. Stored Ore,
(Photographed by Nama Mathieu, 2025).

Photo 68. A year's worth of ore reserves,
(Photographed by Nama Mathieu, 2025).

Photo 69. A stockpile of ore,
(Photographed by Nama Mathieu, 2025).

Photo 70. Coarse rocks to be crushed in an archaic manner in Guido (Sanguié),
(Photographed by Nama Mathieu, 2025).

Photo 71. Archaic crushing by a man in Guido (Sanguié),
(Photographed by Nama Mathieu, 2025).

Photo 72. Archaic crushing by a woman in the Tuy,
by Dera Abasse, 2023.

Photo 73. Modernised crushing method,
(Photographed by Nama Mathieu, 2025).

Photo 74. Modernised coarse rock crusher,
(Photographed by Nama Mathieu, 2025).

Photo 75. Crusher for grinding coarse rocks into rock powder,
(Photographed by Nama Mathieu, 2025).

Photo 76. Crusher for grinding coarse rocks into rock powder,
(Photographed by Nama Mathieu, 2025).

Photo 77. Mills for grinding rock into finer powder,
(Photographed by Nama Mathieu, 2025).

Photo 78. Grinding wheel equipment and device,
(Photographed by Nama Mathieu, 2025).

Photo 79. Mills for grinding rock into finer powder,
(Photographed by Nama Mathieu, 2025).

Photo 80. A powder of rocks,
(Photographed by Nama Mathieu, 2025).

Photo 81. Rock powder stored in bags for washing,
(Photographed by Nama Mathieu, 2025).

Photo 82. A sample of crushed ore to assess its gold content,
(Photographed by Nama Mathieu, 2025).

Photo 83. Archaic testing device,
(Photographed by Nama Mathieu, 2025).

Photo 84. A gold panner in action during testing,
(Photographed by Nama Mathieu, 2025).

Photo 85. Ore washing apparatus,
(Photographed by Nama Mathieu, 2025).

Photo 86. Ore washing,
(Photographed by Nama Mathieu, 2025).

Photo 87. Two washing boards,
by Dera Abasse, 2024.

Photo 88. Washing by a Woman,
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Photo 89. Ore washing by a young man,
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Photo 90. Washing ore by a woman,
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Photo 94. A cyanide tank,
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Photo 95. Interconnection of two cyanide tanks,
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Source: Dera Abasse.

Photo 99. A gold buyer on the site,
Source: Dera Abasse.

Photo 100. Digital jeweller's scale,
Source: Dera Abasse.

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Photo 103. Combination of two generators,
(Photographed by Nama Mathieu, 2025).

Photo 104. Use of solar panels at the gold site,
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Photo 105. Use of motor pumps,
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Photo 106. Generator engine,
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(Photographed by Nama Mathieu, 2025).

Photo 109. Dwelling on the Guido gold site (Réo),
(Photographed by Nama Mathieu, 2025).

Photo 110. Dwelling on the Guido gold site (Réo),
(Photographed by Nama Mathieu, 2025).

Photo 111. Dwelling on the Guido gold site (Réo),
(Photographed by Nama Mathieu, 2025).

Photo 112. Fenced dwelling on Guido's gold site,
(Photographed by Nama Mathieu, 2025).

Photo 113. Doorless dwelling on Guido's gold site,
(Photographed by Nama Mathieu, 2025).

Photos 114(A,B). Toilets at Guido's gold site,
(Photographed by Nama Mathieu, 2025).

Photo 115. General shop on Guido's gold site,
(Photographed by Nama Mathieu, 2025).

Photo 116. Shop on Guido's gold site,
(Photographed by Nama Mathieu, 2025).

Photo 117. A liqueur cellar at Guido's gold site,
(Photographed by Nama Mathieu, 2025).

Photo 118. A bush on Guido's gold site,
(Photographed by Nama Mathieu, 2025).

Photo 119. A restaurant on Guido's gold site,
(Photographed by Nama Mathieu, 2025).

Photo 120. A butchery on Guido's gold site,
(Photographed by Nama Mathieu, 2025).

Photo 121. A restaurant on Guido's golden site,
(Photographed by Nama Mathieu, 2025).

Photo 122. A restaurant worker washing dishes on Guido's golden floor,
(Photographed by Nama Mathieu, 2025).

Photo 123. A cafeteria on Guido's golden floor,
(Photographed by Nama Mathieu, 2025).

Photo 124. A forge point for working materials on Guido's gold,
(Photographed by Nama Mathieu, 2025).